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IRNAZAROV D. T.

Artificial intelligence as a dominant driver of the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures in turbulence

The subject of the research is the theoretical and practical foundations of artificial intelligence as a dominant factor in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures in turbulent conditions.

The aim of the research is to analyze the role of artificial intelligence in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures in conditions of turbulence, as well as to study the main aspects related to the use of AI.

Research methods. The study used a variety of methods that helped to analyze the impact of AI on the economic potential of business structures and adaptation to turbulence. The main research methods used were: analysis of scientific literature and review of theoretical approaches; empirical research; SWOT analysis; systematic approach; scenario analysis; comparative analysis; and tabular and graphical method.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that artificial intelligence plays an important role in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures, especially in conditions of economic turbulence. It has been determined that modern enterprises face a high level of uncertainty, changes in markets, and fluctuations in demand and growing competition. It is proved that the use of artificial intelligence is becoming a key tool for increasing their competitiveness, optimizing business processes and improving the efficiency of resource management. It is determined that one of the main problems in this area is the integration of artificial intelligence into existing management systems of business structures, where many companies are not ready for large-scale implementation of artificial intelligence due to insufficient technological base, low level of digital literacy of personnel or lack of financial resources. The conditions of economic turbulence of business structures, characterized by instability and unpredictability in the economic environment, which can affect enterprises in various ways, are investigated. It is analyzed and found that artificial intelligence has a significant impact on the economic potential of business structures, which is manifested in the following main aspects: optimization of business processes; increase in productivity and efficiency; innovation and development

of new products; adaptability and flexibility; forecasting and risk management; economic benefits and competitive advantages. It is proved that the use of artificial intelligence in turbulent conditions allows business structures to more accurately predict changes in market conditions, adapt to them in real time and reduce the risks associated with external factors. It is determined that artificial intelligence is dominant in shaping the economic potential of business structures, but the effectiveness of its application depends on the ability of organizations to adapt to new obstacles, develop infrastructure and integrate the latest technologies into their business processes.

Scope of the results. Economics, business analysis, management, information technology, economic potential of the enterprise.

Conclusions. Artificial intelligence acts as a dominant factor in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures, especially in times of economic turbulence. The introduction of AI helps business structures to reduce costs, increase efficiency and provide competitive advantages in the face of rapid change and economic turbulence. The conditions of economic turbulence include various factors that can interact and influence the economic environment of business structures, understanding of which and readiness to adapt to which is a key element of successful business management in conditions of uncertainty. Thus, in order to increase their economic potential, business structures need to develop a strategic approach to the introduction of AI and ensure the maximum synergistic effect of its implementation. In the future, AI will become an even more important element of economic potential formation in business strategies, providing business structures with competitive advantages and helping them to respond effectively to new conditions of turbulence.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, business structures, economic potential, formation and development, turbulence conditions, business strategy, innovation, uncertainty.

ІРНАЗАРОВ Д. Т.

Штучний інтелект як домінанта формування та розвитку економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур в умовах турбулентності

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні основи дослідження штучного інтелекту як домінанта формування та розвитку економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур в умовах турбулентності.

Метою дослідження є аналіз ролі штучного інтелекту у формуванні та розвитку економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур в умовах турбулентності, а також вивчення основних аспектів, пов'язаних із використанням штучного інтелекту.

Методи дослідження. При дослідженні використовувались різноманітні методи, які допомогли глибше проаналізувати вплив ШІ на економічний потенціал бізнес–структур та адаптацію до умов турбулентності. Основними методами дослідження були: аналіз наукової літератури та огляд теоретичних підходів; емпіричні дослідження; SWOT–аналіз; системний підхід; сценарний аналіз; порівняльний аналіз, таблично–графічний метод.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що штучний інтелект відіграє важливу роль у формуванні та розвитку економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур, особливо в умовах економічної турбулентності. Визначено, що сучасні підприємства стикаються з високим рівнем невизначеності, змінами на ринках, коливаннями попиту та зростаючою конкуренцією. Доведено, що використання штучного інтелекту стає ключовим інструментом для підвищення їхньої конкурентоспроможності, оптимізації бізнес–процесів та підвищення ефективності управління ресурсами. Визначено, що однією з основних проблем у цій сфері є інтеграція штучного інтелекту в існуючі системи управління бізнес–структур, де безліч компаній не готові до масштабного впровадження штучного інтелекту через недостатню технологічну базу, низький рівень цифрової грамотності персоналу або брак фінансових ресурсів. Досліджено умови економічної турбулентності бізнес–структур, які характеризуються нестабільністю і непередбачуваністю в економічному середовищі, що можуть впливати на підприємства різними способами. Проаналізовано і з'ясовано, що штучний інтелект має значний вплив на економічний потенціал бізнес–структур, що проявляється в основних аспектах: оптимі–

зація бізнес–процесів; підвищення продуктивності та ефективності; інновації та розвиток нових продуктів; адаптивність та гнучкість; прогнозування та управління ризиками; економічна вигода та конкурентні переваги. Доведено, що використання штучного інтелекту в умовах турбулентності дозволяє бізнес–структурам більш точно прогнозувати зміни ринкових умов, адаптуватися до них у реальному часі та знижувати ризики, пов'язані з зовнішніми факторами. Визначено, що штучний інтелект є домінантою у формуванні економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур, але ефективність його застосування залежить від здатності організації адаптуватися до нових перешкод, розвивати інфраструктуру та інтегрувати новітні технології у свої бізнес–процеси.

Галузь застосування результатів. Економіка, бізнес–аналіз, управління, інформаційні технології, економічний потенціал підприємства.

Висновки. Штучний інтелект виступає як домінантний фактор у формуванні та розвитку економічного потенціалу бізнес–структур, особливо в умовах економічної турбулентності. Впровадження ШІ допомагає бізнес–структурам знижувати витрати, підвищувати ефективність і забезпечувати конкурентні переваги в умовах швидких змін і економічної турбулентності. Умови економічної турбулентності включають різноманітні фактори, які можуть взаємодіяти і впливати на економічне середовище бізнес–структур, розуміння і готовність адаптації до яких є ключовим елементом успішного управління бізнесом в умовах невизначеності. Таким чином, для нарощування свого економічного потенціалу бізнес–структурам потрібно розробити стратегічний підхід до впровадження ШІ і забезпечити максимальний синергійний ефект від його імплементації. У подальшому ШІ стане ще важливішим елементом формування економічного потенціалу у бізнес–стратегіях, надаючи бізнес–структурам конкурентні переваги та допомагаючи їм ефективно реагувати на нові умови турбулентності.

Ключові слова: штучний інтелект, бізнес–структури, економічний потенціал, формування та розвиток, умови турбулентності, бізнес–стратегія, інновації, невизначеність.

Formulation of the problem. Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly important role in the formation and development of business structures, especially in times of economic turbulence. Modern businesses face a high level of uncertainty, changes in markets, fluctuations in demand, and growing competition. The use of artificial intelligence is becoming a key tool to increase their competitiveness, optimize business processes, and improve resource management. One of the main challenges in this area is the integration of artificial intelligence into existing business management systems, where many companies are not ready for large–scale implementation of artificial intelligence due to insufficient technological base, low level of digital literacy of staff, or lack of financial resources. In addition, there is the issue of adapting business structures to new conditions, which requires changes in their culture and approaches to decision–making.

The use of AI in turbulent environments allows businesses to more accurately predict changes in market conditions, adapt to them in real time, and reduce risks associated with external factors. However, in order to achieve maximum results, it is necessary to take into account the ethical aspects of AI, possible social consequences, such as job losses due to automation, and to comply with the rules

governing the use of technology. Thus, AI is dominant in shaping the economic potential of business structures, but the effectiveness of its application depends on the organization's ability to adapt to new challenges, develop infrastructure, and integrate the latest technologies into its business processes.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The impact of artificial intelligence on the economic potential of business structures in turbulent times has been the subject of numerous studies by many researchers in various fields, such as economics, business analysis, management, and information technology. Thomas Davenport is one of the leading AI researchers who has analyzed how artificial intelligence helps companies improve productivity, optimize processes, and reduce risks in the face of uncertainty. Mr. Davenport also explored how AI facilitates data–driven decision–making, which is especially important in a rapidly changing environment. Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee analyzed technological innovations, including artificial intelligence, and their impact on business and the economy. The authors argue that AI is becoming a key factor in economic growth and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, especially in the face of market turbulence. Klaus Schwab explored the impact of AI and other technologies of the fourth

industrial revolution on global economic processes and enterprises. The author drew attention to how digital innovations, including AI, are changing business models and creating new opportunities for the development of companies, economic potential in an unstable environment.

Michael Porter examined the impact of the latest technologies, including AI, on the structure and strategies of companies, analyzed how AI can help businesses improve their market position, optimize operational processes, and ensure long-term stability in the face of market uncertainty. Andrew Ng reviewed the practical aspects of using AI to increase the economic potential of enterprises and emphasized the importance of adapting enterprises to new technologies and innovations in a changing environment. Michael Jordan explored how AI algorithms can be used to predict market fluctuations and make strategic decisions in the face of turbulence. The author emphasizes the importance of high-quality big data processing to maximize the effect of AI implementation in business. The contribution of these authors is quite significant, but it requires additional in-depth research into the field of AI application to improve the efficiency of the formation and development of the economic potential of enterprises, taking into account the importance of technological innovation in turbulent conditions.

Presenting main material. Artificial intelligence is becoming a dominant factor in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures in the modern world. In the context of economic turbulence, when market conditions are changing rapidly and uncertainty is growing, the introduction of AI is becoming critical to ensuring competitive advantages and business sustainability and provides business structures with new opportunities to optimize processes, increase efficiency, adapt to a changing environment and create innovative products and services [1; 3; 5; 6; 8]. The conditions of economic turbulence for business structures are characterized by instability and unpredictability in the economic environment, which can affect enterprises in various ways, their understanding is critical for strategic management and adaptation (Table) [2; 4; 7; 9; 10].

Since artificial intelligence affects the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures, we will provide its main definitions (Figure) [12; 14; 15; 16; 18; 19].

The definitions in Fig. 1, cover the main aspects of artificial intelligence and its applications, providing a clear picture of how this technology functions and what opportunities it opens up for various sectors of the economy [11; 13; 17; 20].

Artificial intelligence has a significant impact on the economic potential of business structures, and this impact is manifested in several key aspects: optimization of business processes; increased productivity and efficiency; innovation and new product development; adaptability and flexibility; forecasting and risk management; economic benefits and competitive advantages. Let us consider them in more detail [21; 22; 23].

Optimization of business processes – AI automates repetitive and routine tasks, such as data processing, inventory management, and customer service, which reduces human labor costs, reduces errors, and increases processing speed. Supply chains are being optimized by forecasting demand, automating procurement processes, and improving logistics solutions, which helps reduce inventory management costs and improve delivery.

Increase productivity and efficiency – AI allows you to analyze large amounts of data to identify trends, patterns, and anomalies that help you make more informed decisions, helping to optimize business processes and increase efficiency. It uses customer data to create personalized offers, products, and services, and increases customer satisfaction, loyalty, and sales.

Innovations and new product development – AI is used to create innovative products and services through data analytics, simulations, and modeling, which encourages businesses to respond faster to market changes and reduce the time to develop new products. Opportunities are opening up for new business models, such as data-driven platforms or subscription models, enabling businesses to secure new revenue streams and expand markets.

Adaptability and flexibility – AI allows businesses to adapt more quickly to changes in market conditions, such as fluctuations in demand or economic crises, which helps to avoid negative consequences and take advantage of new opportunities. The introduction of AI allows enterprises to be more flexible in their business processes, which helps them respond more quickly to external challenges, such as changes in regulatory requirements or new competitive threats.

Main conditions of economic turbulence in the economic environment

№	Factor	Subfactor	Description.
1	Economic fluctuations	Financial crises	Sharp and significant fluctuations in financial markets, such as banking crises, stock market crashes, or currency crises, can cause economic instability.
		High inflation or deflation	Rapidly rising prices (inflation) or falling prices (deflation) can lead to changes in the purchasing power of individuals and business spending.
		Changes in interest rates	Decisions by central banks to change interest rates may affect the cost of credit and investment, which will affect economic activity.
2	Political and geopolitical factors	Political instability	Political crises, revolutions, changes of government or instability in a country may affect the business environment and economic conditions.
		Geopolitical conflicts	International conflicts, trade wars, sanctions or political disputes between countries may cause economic turmoil and affect global markets.
3	Changes in legislation and regulation	Regulatory changes	Changes in tax laws, labor laws, environmental standards or other regulatory requirements may affect costs and business processes.
		Consumer protection policies	New rules and regulations affecting the consumer market may change consumer behavior and requirements for products and services.
4	Socio-economic factors	Changes in demographics	Changes in the demographic structure, such as an aging population or a changing labor force structure, may affect labor markets and consumer preferences.
		Social movements	The growth of social or environmental movements can change public opinion and increase demands for corporate social responsibility.
5	Technological changes	Rapid technological progress	New technologies and innovations may radically change market conditions and create new opportunities or threats for businesses.
		Cyber threats	The growing number of cyber threats and attacks may create uncertainty in the security of data and information systems.
6	Natural and environmental factors	Natural disasters	Earthquakes, floods, hurricanes, or other natural disasters can damage infrastructure and business processes.
		Environmental changes	Climate change, environmental disasters, or the depletion of natural resources can affect businesses and their supply chains.
7	Global economic trends	Economic downturn	Global economic downturns may reduce demand for goods and services and affect the overall level of economic activity.
		Trade trends	Changes in global trade flows and patterns may create new opportunities or challenges for businesses.
8	Market changes	Competition	Increased competition from new or international companies may change market dynamics and affect pricing.
		Consumer trends	Changes in consumer preferences or behavior may affect the demand for products and services.

Forecasting and risk management – AI uses data analytics to predict economic and market trends and helps businesses proactively plan their strategy and mitigate risks. Thus, systems are being developed to monitor and manage risks, such as financial fluctuations, supply chain problems, or cyberattacks, which help businesses ensure resilience and reduce potential losses.

Economic benefits and competitive advantages – AI helps to reduce the cost of operational processes, automation, and resource management, which leads to increased profitability and optimization of enter-

prise resources. Also, AI implementation provides businesses with competitive advantages through innovative products, improved efficiency, and the ability to respond quickly to market changes to maintain market leadership and attract new customers.

Thus, artificial intelligence has a significant impact on the economic potential of business structures, which helps to optimize business processes, increase productivity, develop new products and services, ensure adaptability and flexibility, and improve risk forecasting and management [24; 25; 26; 27; 28].

Definitions of artificial intelligence covering relevant aspects of the economy^a

Source: [11–17]

Conclusions

Artificial intelligence acts as a dominant factor in the formation and development of the economic potential of business structures, especially in times of economic turbulence. The introduction of AI helps business structures to reduce costs, increase efficiency, and provide competitive advantages in the face of rapid change and economic turbulence. The conditions of economic turbulence include various factors that can interact and influence the economic environment of business structures, understanding of which and readiness to adapt to which is a key element of successful business management in conditions of uncertainty. Thus, in order to increase their economic potential, business structures need to develop a strategic approach to the introduction of AI and ensure the maximum synergistic effect of its implementation. In the future, AI will become an even more important element of economic potential formation in business strategies, giving businesses competitive

advantages and helping them to respond effectively to new turbulent conditions.

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